

ISLAMIC ECONOMY IN VIII-IX CENTURIES FORMATION OF THEORETICAL AND PHILOSOPHICAL BASIS

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Abstract. In the article, the socio-philosophical ideas and teachings of the peoples of the Middle Ages and the Middle East were formed and developed on the basis of the religious ideology that defines the spiritual and moral way of life, the Islamic economy reached the peak of its development in the first half of the 9th century, the formation of the Muslim tax system based on Sharia in the caliphate, Islamic economic norms It has been thoroughly studied by scholars, and the development of its theoretical aspects has been philosophically analyzed.

Keywords. Abu Yusuf, Qudoma ibn Ja'far, Yahya ibn Adam, Muhammad al-Shaybani, al-Dawudi, al-Mawardi, Ghazali, Ibn Khaldun, Ibn Taymiyya, jurisprudence, Islamic economics.

The tax system in Muslim law was formed on the basis of Sharia after the establishment of the Islamic state. Taxes play an important role in the formation and development of the financial power of the Arab Caliphate. The tax system of the Arab caliphate, based on Sharia rules, was a rather complex structure. Nevertheless, this system was thoroughly studied by scholars, its theoretical aspects were developed, and a tax system was created based on Islamic law. Taxes based on Islamic tax law include: zakat, ushr, khums, jizya, khiraj.¹

1. Rakhmanov. A. R. Islamic law. - Tashkent: Generation of the new century. 2003. – S. 479.

Economic issues in Islamic economic thought have been considered by various Muslim scholars. It is common to analyze Islamic economics according to the following criteria.

First, some economic issues mentioned in the Holy Qur'an, including the prohibition of usury and the support of economic activities for people's well-being, are discussed and commented by the commentators. Secondly, some economic issues are studied from a jurisprudential point of view. Thirdly, the importance of economic issues in the development of the Islamic moral system has been studied. In particular, the works of scientists, Sufis, Muslim philosophers belong to this category. Fourthly, some works on Islamic economics were written by the scholars while they held important government positions based on the needs of their time. Matters related to public finances, revenues and expenses, and tax revenues fall into this category. Fifth, Islamic economic relations have been objectively analyzed by some Islamic scholars and philosophers. Scholars such as Imam Ghazali, Ibn Taymiyya, and Ibn Khaldun can be included in this category.

Works on the Islamic economy and tax system can be found in many Muslim countries. In the early days of Islam, more than 20 books on taxation were known. The first works on the Islamic tax system were written in the 8th century. But only three have reached our days. The first of these books was written by Muawiya ibn Ubaydullah al-Ash'ari, the minister of the umma caliph Mahdi. The works of Abu Yusuf, al-Qurayshi, Abu Ubayd, Yahya ibn Adam, Qudama ibn Ja'far, al-Dawudi, Ibn Zanjawayh, al-Mahzumi have survived to us².

Abu Yusuf (735-798) made a great contribution to the formation of the caliphate tax system. Abu Yusuf's "Kitab ul-Kharaj" treatise on the problems of taxation is the first treatise covering economic issues in the Islamic world. He wrote this book during his tenure as the chief judge of the Abbasid Caliphate in 174-182 AH.

² Abdul Azim Islahi. Contribution of Muslim Scholars to Economic Thought and Analysis. - Jeddah. 2014. – R.61.

The famous narrator Yahya ibn Adam (757-818) wrote "Kitab ul-Kharaj" based on hadiths, jurisprudence, and wise sayings³. The work of Yahya ibn Adam deals with tax issues: land taxation, land ownership, land use procedure, etc.

The author of another work on Islamic taxation is Qudoma ibn Ja'far (864-932), whose work "Kitab ul-Kharaj" was written in order to prove that the tax system in force at that time was fully compatible with the requirements of Sharia⁴.

Jurisprudence scholar Muhammad al-Shaybani's book "Kitab al-Iktisab" covers small economic relations. In addition to the public finance or tax system, if attention is focused on the issues of production, value and distribution of consumer products, we can see that macroeconomic relations in Islam are covered in the book "Kitab ul-Amwal" written by the great scholar Abu Ubaid⁵.

Also, al-Dawudi (died 1012) as a representative of the Maliki madhhab, in his work "Kitab ul-amvol", the problems of tax and land management were considered from the perspective of Maliki. Al-Mawardi (d. 1058) wrote about the state administration in the work "Ahkom ul-Sultaniya" about state revenues and expenses, public lands, state privileges and the procedure for granting land by the government. Ibn Hazm's (d. 1064) book "Kitab ul-Muhalla" covers many economic issues and discusses the state's financial management in detail⁶.

Later al-Ghazzali (1055-1111) emphasized in his writings that economic thinking is an integral part of the Islamic way of life, and in his book "Profit and Trade" he discussed buying and selling, advance payment of money, legal and illegal methods of income, economic justice, economics and shed light on the relationship between religion⁷. Ibn Taymiyyah (1263-1328) expressed his economic ideas in al-Hisba fil-Islam (Public Obligations in Islam) in a state governed by a ruler who

³ Yahya ibn Adam. Kitab al-kharaj. Khrestomatia po istorii Khalifata. Sost. thread A.I. Nadiradze. - M.: Izd-vo MGU. 1968. - S.249.

⁴ Mekhamadiev E.A. Arab historian X c. Kudama ibn Djafar i doljnost domestika schol v Byzantii: Problema proiskhojdeniya. Vestnik TvGU. Series "History". 2015. No. 3. - S. 33-47.

⁵ Nasir Nabi Bhat. Some Insights in the Development of Islamic Economic Thought During Medieval Times. Asian Journal of Multidisciplinary Studies. Volume 3, Issue 3, March 2015. - R. 161.

⁶ Al-Mawardi. Kitab al-Din val-Duniya. - Beirut: Dar Ihya al-Turath al-Arabi. 1979. -P.194.

Abdul Azim Islahi. Contribution of Muslim Scholars to Economic Thought and Analysis. - Jeddah. 2014. - P.15.

morally leads to a prosperous life in accordance with the Sharia, and emphasized that the provision of freedom of private property in a state would promote the development of society. Ibn Khaldun's (1332-1404) work "Introduction" provides information on some economic issues - division of labor, money and prices, tax system, trade, state revenues and expenses, and others.

Ibn Taymiyyah (1263-1328) expressed his economic ideas in al-Hisba fil-Islam (Public Obligations in Islam) in a state governed by a ruler who morally leads to a prosperous life in accordance with the Sharia, and emphasized that the provision of freedom of private property in a state would promote the development of society. Ibn Khaldun's (1332-1404) work "Introduction" provides information on some economic issues - division of labor, money and prices, tax system, trade, state revenues and expenses, and others. b) The research of a number of economic issues of urgent importance for their time by Muslim scholars, who relied on the rules of Islamic Sharia, had a great impact on the development of Islamic economic doctrine.

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